

Academic Achievement of Students in Kenya's Public Secondary Schools: The Effects of Teacher Time Management and Class Attendance

Mark Mang'oli Fundia

Postgraduate Student, Department of Educational Planning & Management, School of Education, Kibabii University, Kenya

Sarah Naliaka Likoko

Lecturer, Department of Educational Planning & Management, School of Education, Kibabii University, Kenya

Caleb Mackatiani

Senior Lecturer, University of Nairobi, Kenya

Suggested Citation

Fundia, M.M., Likoko, S.N. & Mackatiani, C. (2023). Academic Achievement of Students in Kenya's Public Secondary Schools: The Effects of Teacher Time Management and Class Attendance. *European Journal of Theoretical and Applied Sciences*, 1(5), 675-680.
DOI: [10.59324/ejtas.2023.1\(5\).57](https://doi.org/10.59324/ejtas.2023.1(5).57)

Abstract:

Almost all firms use performance appraisal as one of the strategic tools in human resource management to get a competitive edge. Every employee's performance is identified, measured, and evaluated during this procedure. One of the fundamental instruments that encourages employees to be highly productive and engaged at work is the Teacher Performance Appraisal Development (TPAD). The system of teacher performance appraisal is intended to increase student learning outcomes by positively influencing teachers' professional growth if it is properly developed and put into practice. In general, many schools, particularly those in West Pokot Sub County's rural areas, have performed poorly. The study was designed

to investigate teachers' time management and lesson attendance on students' academic achievement in public secondary schools. A descriptive survey research design was used in the study. The target population was 43 public secondary schools, which had 12900 pupils, 86 Quality Assurance and Standard Officers, 43 principals, 43 deputy Principals, and 860 teachers. The Yamane formula was used to determine the sample size of 388. Sample size is the number of participants included in a study. Interviews, interview schedules, and questionnaires were all used as data gathering tools. A pilot study was conducted to evaluate the validity and reliability of the research instruments used to measure accuracy, consistency, and the degree to which differences in measurement results accurately represented differences between respondents. Additionally, important was the Cronbach alpha. Data analysis benefited from the use of the statistical package for social sciences version 27. The significant levels of one variable were transferred to the other with the use of the multiple regression analysis. Each variable's correlation coefficient was calculated after an Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) test. The study found that student performance on the Kenya Certificate of Secondary Education (KCSE) is favourably and significantly influenced by teacher time management and lesson attendance.

Keywords: *Academic, Achievement, Attendance, Management, Time.*

Introduction

Simple random sampling was employed to include students from a pedagogical institution in an exploratory study (Solvi et al., 2017) on time management and professional identity of students of pedagogical universities. The study found that both academic and non-academic achievement are significantly influenced by an individual's capacity for effective time management. Instead of examining the impact of teachers' time management on students' academic achievement, the study concentrated on students' time management. Worldwide, time is a tremendously valuable resource. According to Kayode and Ayodele (2015), time management skills of teachers may improve students' academic performance. Time is a limited resource that influences many parts of human endeavors, including the education sector. In most circumstances, how effectively one uses their time indicates success and advancement.

T.S.C. Circular No. 12/2017, dated June 5th, as cited by Dorothy and Bonn (2017) in their analysis of a report from the field teacher management officers to headquarters shows that the use of Teacher Performance Appraisal Development (TPAD) has improved teachers' ability to manage their time effectively. The use of TPAD and Performance Contract (PC) has significantly decreased instructors' absences from work and from lessons. At the principals' annual meeting in Mombasa in June 2015, Teacher Service Commission (TSC) Chief Executive Officer Nancy Macharia reaffirmed this. She stated that the use of TPAD has improved teacher time management, which has resulted in higher-quality instruction. The goal of Kimeli and Solomon's study from 2021, Teacher Time Management on Student Examination Scores, was to determine how much teacher time management affects students' test results in Kenyan public secondary schools. The study's findings showed that, with a mean of 4.71 and a standard deviation of 1.283, scheduling assignments effectively has a significant impact on students' test scores. Student exam scores are

influenced by the teacher's time management skills by a mean of 4.12 and SD of 0.922. Student exam scores, with a mean of 4.01 and SD of 0.946, are influenced by proper adherence to the instructional schedule. Timely coverage of the curriculum had an impact on student exam scores, according to a mean of 3.99 and a standard deviation of 0.822. Finally, a mean of 3.65 and a standard deviation of 1.231 agreed that punctuality (showing up for lessons on time) affects students' test scores. The findings of the study that examined the relationship between teachers' time management and students' academic performance in Kenyan public secondary schools found a statistically significant and strong positive correlation between teachers' time management and students' exam scores ($r=0.846$, $p<0.05$).

Teachers were falling behind on important areas of curriculum implementation due to poor time management, according to a study conducted by Robert (2014) on the effects of TPAD on curriculum implementation among teachers in Canada. Teachers are expected to be efficient time managers who consistently save time during the teacher evaluation process. They must make the most of their time and always ensure that each second is valuable. Time is a "infinitely divisible and useable commodity," according to Nasrullah and Khan (2015), who highlighted the importance of time management. They compared time management to a scenario in which a person tries to manage his limited resources in order to achieve greater objectives. A good use of the time would guarantee that the required amount of material would be covered. If lessons don't go to waste, the scheduled material will be covered in the allotted time. Teachers are good time managers, therefore they will always be on time, which will ensure that students are fully engaged in the lesson. Allow time for the content covered to be reviewed and revised because this will eventually result in early syllabus coverage. This will guarantee topic mastery, which will result in pupils passing the exams, which will ultimately mean that the high academic standards and achievement of the learners are satisfied (Munguti and Kanyanjua,

2017) The majority of teachers and students do not report to school on the first day of opening, most teachers write their schemes of work when schools open, go to class without lesson plans, assemblies take longer and eat up classroom time, according to Karimi & Hussain's (2011) descriptive study on time management behavior among secondary school personnel in Kinango District, Coast Province, in Kenya. The effect of teachers' time management on students' academic achievement was not examined in this study. Additionally, it omitted the principals' and students' perspectives.

According to Muriuki (2016), students develop this practice because they observe their professors' dedication to effective time management. Students pick up time management skills. Utilizing time management strategies reduces stress, increases productivity, and boosts people's level of job and life happiness (Hanley et al.,2015). Bakhda (2014) provide evidence on the link between students' academic success and proper time management and focus. Additionally, they learn that time lost can never be made up. They develop self-discipline to make sure they make the most of their study time. As a result, they develop self-discipline because they spend most of their time studying rather than sneaking out or skipping class. Such students would never consider planning strikes or protests that would interfere with their schoolwork. They will put their all effort into making things better.

Records of involvement in professional learning communities both inside and outside of the classroom, initiatives being carried out in conjunction with learning communities, parental and guardian involvement, learner involvement in community service, joint activities with stakeholders, parent and guardian involvement,

invitation letters, attendance lists, activity reports, and program project reports.

Materials and Methods

Research Design

A research design is a strategy for acquiring and examining data in order to answer the study's research questions. A descriptive survey and a correlation research approach were employed in the study. A correlation design was useful in assessing whether there was a relationship between the independent and dependent variables, and a descriptive survey was used to describe the status and conditions surrounding teacher performance reviews. The strategy for collecting, measuring, and analyzing the data is a research design (Kothari & Garg, 2014). The data were gathered through surveys and interview schedules.

Target Population

A whole group of individuals or elements that share at least one characteristic is referred to as a population. (2013) Mbizi et al. The 43 public secondary schools in West Pokot Sub County comprised the study's target population of 13932, which included 860 instructors, 12900 students, 86 principals and their deputy principals, and 86 Quality Assurance and Standard Officers(QASO).

Sampling Procedure and Sample Size

The object or source from which a sample is taken is known as a sampling frame. The frame is arranged logically and methodically. (Victor Jupp; Roger Sapsford 29 March 2006) For the study, a sample of 388 respondents was adequate.

Table 1. Sample Size

Sub County	Total population	Sample size
Teachers	860	24
Principals	86	2
Students	12900	360
QASO	86	2
TOTAL	13932	388

Source: Field Data (2023)

Results

Relationship between Teacher Time Management and Student Academic Performance

Table 2. Description of Variables in the Study Under Teacher Time Management

Var.	Variable label	Variable scale	Variable value
professional_documents+	Teachers ensure timely preparation of professional documents	Ordinal	1-strongly disagree, 2 disagree, 3 agree, 4-strongly agree
Timetable	Teachers ensure all lessons are taught as per the school timetable	Ordinal	1-strongly disagree, 2 disagree, 3 agree, 4-strongly agree
Objectives	Teachers ensure that every lesson has lesson objectives	Ordinal	1-strongly disagree, 2 disagree, 3 agree, 4-strongly agree
Target	Teachers and learners set academic target (mean grade) for each of their classes	Ordinal	1-strongly disagree, 2 disagree, 3 agree, 4-strongly agree
Feedback	Teachers ensure exams are set, marked and feedback given as per the set deadlines	Ordinal	1-strongly disagree, 2 disagree, 3 agree, 4-strongly agree
Environment	Teachers and learners ensure that the learning environment is child friendly, safe and conducive for learning	Ordinal	1-strongly disagree, 2 disagree, 3 agree, 4-strongly agree
Legal_provision	Teachers demonstrate an understanding of legal provision in education and the implication of non-compliance.	Ordinal	1-strongly disagree, 2 disagree, 3 agree, 4-strongly agree
nurture	Teachers identify and nurture learners talent in at least one co-curricular activities	Ordinal	1-strongly disagree, 2 disagree, 3 agree, 4-strongly agree
meetings	Teachers plan and participate in teachers, parents and learners meetings	Ordinal	1-strongly disagree, 2 disagree, 3 agree, 4-strongly agree
punctuality	Teachers maintain punctuality in reporting for duty and lesson attendance	Ordinal	1-strongly disagree, 2 disagree, 3 agree, 4-strongly agree
gaps	Teachers identify individual performance gaps and seek solutions through professional development courses.	Ordinal	1-strongly disagree, 2 disagree, 3 agree, 4-strongly agree

Table 3. Time Management and Student Academic Performance

N=24	Mean	Std. Deviation
Teachers ensure timely preparation of professional documents	4.0000	.39477
Teachers ensure all lessons are taught as per the school timetable	3.9872	.37774
Teachers ensure that every lesson has lesson objectives	2.3718	1.07340
Teachers and learners set academic target (mean grade) for each of their classes	3.1923	1.00722
Teachers ensure exams are set, marked and feedback given as per the set deadlines	2.3462	1.03292
Teachers and learners ensure that the learning environment is child friendly, safe and conducive for learning	2.0641	.40579
Teachers demonstrate an understanding of legal provision in education and the implication of non-compliance.	2.3333	1.01183
Teachers identify and nurture learners talent in at least one co-curricular activities	2.0641	.40579
Teachers plan and participate in teachers, parents and learners meetings	2.0256	.45511
Teachers maintain punctuality in reporting for duty and lesson attendance	2.0513	.42327
Teachers identify individual performance gaps and seek solutions through professional development courses.	2.3949	1.02386
Valid N (listwise)		

The results in table 3 show that the respondents agree (mean 3.00) that Teachers ensure timely preparation of professional documents,

Teachers and learners set academic target (mean grade) for each of their classes and Teachers ensure all lessons are taught as per the school

timetable. However, they disagree (men 2.00) that; Teachers ensure that every lesson has lesson objectives, Teachers and learners set academic target (mean grade) for each of their classes, Teachers ensure exams are set, marked and feedback given as per the set deadlines, Teachers and learners ensure that the learning environment is child friendly, safe and conducive for learning, Teachers demonstrate an understanding of legal provision in education

and the implication of non-compliance, Teachers identify and nurture learners talent in at least one co-curricular activities, Teachers plan and participate in teachers, parents and learners meetings, Teachers maintain punctuality in reporting for duty and lesson attendance and that the Teachers identify individual performance gaps and seek solutions through professional development courses.

Table 4. Correlations between Teacher Time Management and Student Academic Performance

		KCSE Performance	Time Management
KCSE Performance	Pearson Correlation	1	.714**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	120	24
Time Management	Pearson Correlation	.714**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	24	78

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

The analysis results in table 4 show that there was a positive and significant relationship between teacher time management and students' performance in Mathematics in KCSE at $r = .714^{**}$, $P < .01$. These findings are in agreement with an exploratory study done in Russia by (Solvi *et al*, 2017) on time management and professional identity of students of pedagogical universities which revealed that ability of using individual skills of time management, was an important factor in educational and non-educational success.

Conclusion

The study found that teacher lesson attendance (time management) and student academic observation had a favorable and significant impact on students' KCSE performance. Furthermore, it was discovered that the majority of the teachers who responded agreed that teachers' time management had an impact on students' academic success. This indicates that teachers' use of time affects their pupils' academic success. The effect of teachers' time management on pupils' academic progress was also emphasized. The results showed that most

teachers who responded regarded the impact of teachers' time management on students' academic progress as high, with some rating it as extremely high. This implies that teachers' time management affects pupils' academic progress.

Acknowledgement

I want to express my gratitude to Dr. Caleb Mackatiani and Dr. Sarah Likoko, my research supervisors, for taking the time to mentor me during the article writing and the entire Master Degree research process.

Conflict of interests

Authors declared no conflict of interest.

References

- Bakhda, S. (2014). *Management and Evaluation of Schools*. Oxford University Press.
- Kayode, G.M., & Ayodele, J.B. (2015). Impacts of teachers' time management on secondary school students' academic performance in Ekiti

State, Nigeria. *International Journal of Secondary Education*, 3(1), 1-7.
<https://doi.org/10.11648/j.ijsedu.20150301.11>

Mugenda, O.M. & Mugenda, A.G. (2008). *Research Methods, Qualitative and Quantitative approaches*. Nairobi: Acts Press.

Munguti, B. K., & Kanyanjua, D. (2017). Performance appraisals practices and employee productivity in Kenya: A case study of Savannah Cement Ltd. *International Academic Journal of Human Resource and Business Administration*, 2(4), 82-96.

Muriuki, C. W. (2016). *Effect of Performance Appraisal on Employee Motivation at Ministry of East African Community, Labour And Social Protection*.

Doctoral dissertation, School Of Business, University Of Nairobi.

Nasrullah, S., & Khan, M. S. (2015). The impact of time management on the students' academic achievements. *Journal of Literature, Languages and Linguistics*, 11, 66-71

Robert, T. (2014). *Administrator's views on Teacher Evaluation: Examining Ontario's Teacher Performance Appraisal*. OISE, University of Toronto

Solvi, G., Elstad, E. & Hakonkavtl (2017). Teacher evaluation as a wicked policy problem. *Assessment in education principles policy and Practice*, 25(8), 1-19.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/0969594X.2018.1429388>